

PHYSICAL SCIENCES

ABOUT THE MECHANISM OF GRAPHITE SPLITTING

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Abstract

The article provides a review of experimental work on the production of graphene by processing graphite and a review of mathematical models for the splitting of layered structures. Next, the surface layer of graphite, from where the splitting of layered materials begins, is examined for the first time. The graphite layer, which we denote as $R(I)$, its thickness according to our model is $R(I)_a = 1.07$ nm and $R(I)_c = 2.92$ nm, that is, it is a nanostructure. This layer contains 4 sheets of graphene. This means that the $R(I)$ layer will more easily move along the cleavage plane. Moreover, at the stages of easy sliding, linear and parabolic strain hardening, as well as at the stage of preliminary destruction, the observed localization patterns are different types of wave processes. At the boundary of the $R(I)$ layer with the bulk phase, internal stresses arise due to relaxation or reconstruction of the surface. Next, we will build a theoretical model of graphite, presenting it in the form of a cylinder of finite dimensions, and use our modified work, supplementing it with homogeneous boundary conditions. The model we obtained for the splitting of graphite mathematically coincides with Stefan's fourth problem, where the freezing of ice is considered, and the movement of phase boundaries $\beta(t) = \beta_0 \sqrt{t}$ is called the self-similar law of motion. We have shown that to split graphite into graphene sheets, it is necessary to expend work that exceeds the adhesion energy of the $R(I)$ layer from the rest of the volume. It has also been shown that it is much easier to obtain graphene mechanically (including ultrasonic splitting) than by changing the temperature gradient. However, graphene-like structures can be obtained using a pulsed picosecond laser for heating.

Keywords: graphite, graphene, surface layer, nanostructure, Stefan problem, surface, splitting, delamination, crystal.

Introduction

Graphene is a two-dimensional single-layer sheet of sp^2 -hybridized carbon atoms arranged in hexagonal shapes. The presence of strong covalent C-C σ -bonds in the plane of the graphene sheet in combination with π -electrons outside it determines the unique physical and chemical properties of graphene, such as a large theoretical specific surface area (~ 2600 m²/g) [1], high mobility of charge carriers (~ 200000 cm²/V s) [2], high Young's modulus (~ 1000 GPa) [3], thermal conductivity (~ 5000 W/m K) [4], optical transparency ($\sim 97.7\%$) [5], mechanical strength, chemical stability, etc. To obtain graphene from graphite, there are several methods, which we will briefly review below.

The purpose of this article is a theoretical model of the splitting of graphite, with the aim of obtaining graphene and graphene-like structures from it.

Methods for obtaining graphene structures

Mechanical splitting. This is the first method for synthesizing graphene, a method in which longitudinal or transverse stress is created on the surface of materi-

als with a layered structure. Graphite is a layered material consisting of many layers of graphene, which are interconnected by relatively weak van der Waals forces (VDWs). Therefore, if you apply longitudinal or transverse stress to it, thereby breaking weak airborne forces, you can obtain individual sheets or stacks of graphene-like structures (Figure 1a). Highly oriented pyrolytic graphite, single-crystalline graphite or natural graphite are used as the starting material in this method [6-8]. Cleavage can be performed using various means, such as the Scotch-tape method [9], ultrasonic treatment [10], electrochemical synthesis [11], transfer printing method [12] and many others.

Thermal splitting. Thermal decomposition also makes it possible to obtain few-layer graphene structures (MLS). The process is carried out at high (more than 1000 °C) and low (about 100 °C) temperatures, at different heating rates, in the environment of various gases (hydrogen, argon, etc.) and in vacuum, using graphite or its derivatives, thereby obtaining most graphene structures of various shapes and sizes.

Figure 1. Scheme for obtaining graphene samples by micromechanical splitting (a); device for thermal splitting (see text) (b).

The device (Figure 1b) is illustrated by a circuit diagram from the Patent [13]. Control panel 1 includes controls and devices for monitoring the operating mode of the device. The splitting unit 2 contains three reactor pipes 3. To supply electrical supply voltage to the end sections of the reactor pipes 3, copper water-cooled current leads 4 are used. The TRG entering the cavity of the heaters 3 in the ascending air flow through three pipelines 5 settles in the receiving hopper 6. To ensure For water cooling of the reactor pipes of the device, a ballast tank 7 with water is used, from which coolant is circulated through valve 8 by means of pump 9. The three-phase power supply unit 10 contains three step-down furnace transformers and three groups of thyristors with fuses and RC filters. At the bottom of the splitting unit 2 there is a centrifugal fan 11 for air supply. Continuous supply of initial oxidized graphite is carried out by block 12 of three parallel screw feeders driven through gear 13 by an electric motor 14. Oxidized graphite powder is periodically added by the operator to the supply hopper 15. To smoothly regulate air flow, three ball valves 16 are used. For example, when using

high-temperature splitting processes can occur in seconds [14]. Graphite oxide or intercalated graphite compounds are used as starting materials for thermal decomposition instead of pure graphite.

Ultrasonic splitting. The first successful decomposition of graphite by ultrasonic treatment was achieved in the organic solvent N-methylpyrrolidone [15]. The exfoliation of graphite by ultrasonic treatment in the presence of surfactants has also been proposed. This was first reported in [16], in which dodecylbenzenesulfonate was used as a surfactant. Works [17, 18] show that graphene structures obtained by ultrasonic processing of graphite and its derivatives contain a lot of oxygen. In [19], multilayer graphene was obtained by ultrasonic splitting of graphite microparticles in a surface-active solvent, a mixture of nonane and water, and a surface-active surfactant was selected that ensures the dispersion of graphene in hydrophilic systems. In [20], a technology was developed for producing polymers modified with graphene structures using ultrasonic dispersion (Fig. 2).

Figure 2. Diagram (a) and appearance (b) of the ultrasonic unit of the installation for liquid-phase stratification of graphite [20]: 1 – ultrasonic generator; 2 – magnetostrictive transducer; 3 – waveguide; 4 – pressure gauge; 5 – cavitometer; 6 – drain hole; 7 – overpressure valve; 8 – sealing gasket; 9 – finely dispersed graphite; 10 – solvent; 11 – pressure chamber.

Chemical degradation. Chemical digestion is a multi-step process. At the first stage, intercalated graphite compounds are obtained [21].

Figure 3. Routes to obtain graphene through the cleavage of various precursors

The Hummers method [22] involves the oxidation of graphite powder with strong oxidizing agents such as KMnO_4 and NaNO_3 into H_2SO_4 or H_3PO_4 [22, 23]. This leads to oxidation of the internal layers of graphite and, as a consequence, to an increase in the interlayer distance in the crystal and, accordingly, to a decrease in the interaction energy between the layers. The chemical method implies several possible options for preparing

graphene-containing suspensions (Fig. 3). At the second stage, the resulting graphene oxide is reduced to obtain MGS [24].

Chemical vapor deposition (CVD). Already in 1976, it was known about the synthesis of graphite on nickel. It was shown that at a temperature of $900\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ on a metal substrate it is possible to form a graphite film with a thickness of $400\text{ \AA}$ [25-30]. The mechanism of formation of a graphite-like film is very simple (Fig. 4).

Figure 4. Scheme of the formation of a graphene film on the surface of nickel or copper using the chemical vapor deposition method.

In a mixture of carbon-containing gas, hydrogen and argon at various pressures (from several fractions of a millitorr to atmospheric pressure), upon heating, decomposition into carbon and components occurs at temperatures below 400 °C. Further, as the temperature increases, carbon atoms are deposited onto the nickel substrate, starting at 650 °C. At temperatures above 800 °C they begin to diffuse into the bulk of nickel. Heating stops at temperatures of 950-1000 °C, and then, when the sample is cooled to room temperature, the crystal lattice of the metal (due to thermal compression) squeezes carbon atoms onto the surface, where they form a graphite-like structure, since the lattice constant of nickel is very close to the lattice constant of graphite. By selecting certain synthesis parameters, such as the thickness of the nickel film, the maximum synthesis temperature, the synthesis time and the cooling rate of the sample, it is possible to achieve the formation of a thin graphene film - up to obtaining a graphene monolayer.

Figure 5. Schematic representation of the main processes occurring during the epitaxial growth of graphene from hydrocarbon molecules E. They are deposited on the surface, undergoing decomposition through a series of dehydrogenation reactions leading to different types of C_xH_y , shown as E and H atoms. New species diffuse through the surface. The smaller forms of carbon M and D do not diffuse, but stick together into larger clusters of C atoms. The H atoms of the parent molecule migrate from the surface and form a hydrogen molecule, which evaporates from the surface. And finally, some of the forms such as M and D, or even their large clusters C, may attach to the island of G at its edge (a); A type of epitaxial growth of graphene is the thermal decomposition of silicon carbide. When SiC is heated to 1300 °C in an ultra-high vacuum, silicon sublimation occurs, resulting in the formation of graphene layers on the surface of the crystal (b).

Other methods for producing graphene. Let's list some of them. In [36], the possibility of electrochemical intercalation of the tetrafluoroborate anion into graphite from a supercritical electrolyte based on carbon dioxide, acetonitrile as a cosolvent, and tetrabutylammonium tetrafluoroborate salt was shown for the first time.

In [37], the task was set: to develop a technology for producing graphene films using the method of dissociative evaporation (sublimation) of the SiC surface and to study the possibility of instrumental applications of the resulting structures.

In [38], the task was set: to develop a method of plasma-electrochemical splitting of graphite to obtain nanocomposites, which are few-layer graphene structures doped with nitrogen atoms and decorated with transition metal oxides, which have a set of necessary characteristics for their use as effective platinum-free

Epitaxial growth. Epitaxial growth of graphene on metal surfaces of crystals such as ruthenium, iridium, platinum, palladium, nickel, etc. [31-33]. This method is based on the increasing nature of the temperature dependence of carbon solubility in transition metals. At temperatures exceeding 1000 °C, in the presence of any carbon source, metal saturation occurs as a result of chemical deposition of carbon from the gas phase. Further, in a high or ultra-high vacuum at a pressure of 10-10 millibars and a decrease in the substrate temperature, the solubility of carbon in the metal drops significantly, and due to thermal compression of the crystal lattice, carbon comes to the surface, forming graphene domains of a large area (Fig. 5a). Sublimation of silicon from a SiC substrate at high temperature (~1000 °C), leading to graphitization of the silicon carbide surface (Fig. 5b), is also one of the promising methods for obtaining high-quality graphene samples (from single-layer graphene to graphene containing several layers) with a size of ~100 nm (with a crystallite size of up to 50 μm) [34, 35].

catalysts for the reduction of oxygen in fuel cathodes elements.

As a result: the synthesis of graphene and graphene-like materials is based on increasing the interplanar distance, weakening the van der Waals interaction forces between graphene layers with subsequent delamination of graphite.

Theory of splitting or delamination of layered structures

Classification of layered inorganic compounds [39].

The layered structure of the substance is characterized by strong interactions in two orthogonal directions and several orders of magnitude weaker interactions in the third orthogonal direction. The most famous example of substances with a layered structure is graphite (see above), in which layers formed by covalently bonded carbon atoms in sp^2 hybridization (with a binding energy of ≈ 524 kJ/mol) are connected by van der

Waals forces (with a binding energy of ≈ 7 kJ/mol) [26]. Table 1 shows the classification of layered materials according to the presence and absence of charge in their constituent layers.

Layered materials can be classified by comparing the forces that hold the layers together. These are, first of all, electrostatic, hydrogen and van der Waals interactions.

Table 1.

Classification of layered inorganic materials by type of layers [39].	
Uncharged layers	Chemical composition
Non-conducting layers (dielectrics)	
clay	
kaolinite	$\text{Al}_2\text{Si}_2\text{O}_5(\text{OH})_4$
serpentine	$\text{Mg}_3\text{Si}_2\text{O}_5(\text{OH})$
Nickel cyanide	$\text{Ni}(\text{CN})_2$
hexagonal boron nitride	h-BN
Electrically conductive layers	
graphite	C
transition metal dichalcogenides	MX_2 (M = Ti, Zr, Hf, V, Nb, Ta, Bi, Mo, W; X = S, Se, Te)
Metal carbides and nitrides, MAX and MXene phases	$\text{M}_{n+1}(\text{A})_m\text{X}_n$ (n=1-3; m= 0,1; M – Ti, Zr, Hf, V, Nb, Ta, Bi, Mo, W; A – Si, Ge, Al, S, Sn; X – C, N)
metal oxyphosphates	MOPO_4 (M = V, Nb, Ta)
Charged layers	
Negatively charged layers	
clay	
montmorillonite	$\text{Na}_x(\text{Al}_{2-x}\text{Mg}_x)(\text{Si}_4\text{O}_{10})(\text{OH})_2$
saponite	$\text{Ca}_{x/2}\text{Mg}_3(\text{Al}_x\text{Si}_{4-x}\text{O}_{10})(\text{OH})_2$
vermiculite	$(\text{Na,Ca})_x(\text{Mg}_{3-x}\text{Li}_x\text{Si}_4\text{O}_{10})(\text{OH})_2$
muscovite	$\text{KAl}_2(\text{AlSi}_3\text{O}_{10})(\text{OH})_2$
β -alumina	$\text{NaAl}_{11}\text{O}_{17}$
complex oxides of transition and alkali metals	M^IXO_2 (M^I – alkali metal; X = Ti, V, Cr, Mn, Co, Ni)
layered perovskites Ruddlesden–Popper phases	$\text{M}_{n+1}\text{X}_n\text{O}_{3n+1}$ (M - elements I-III группы; X – transition elements)
Dion–Jacobson phases	$\text{M}^I\text{Ln}_{n-1}\text{X}_n\text{O}_{3n+1}$ (M^I - alkali metal; $\text{Ln} = \text{P3}\bar{\text{O}}$; X = Nb, Ta)
Aurivillius phases	$(\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_2)\text{M}_{n-1}\text{X}_n\text{O}_{3n+1}$ (M – elements I-III; X – transition elements)
Positively charged layers	
layered double hydroxides	$[\text{M}^{2+}_{1-x}\text{M}^{3+}_x(\text{OH})_2]_n\text{A}_{n-x/n}\cdot m\text{H}_2\text{O}$
layered transition hydroxides metals	$\text{M}_2(\text{OH})_3\text{X}$ ($\text{M}^{\text{II}} = \text{Co, Cu, Ni, Mn, Zn}$ и X = $\text{NO}_3^-, \text{CH}_3\text{CO}_2^-, \text{Cl}^-$)
layered REE hydroxides class LREH-I	$\text{Ln}_2(\text{OH})_5(\text{A}^{m-})_{1/m}\cdot n\text{H}_2\text{O}$ ($\text{Ln} = \text{REE}$, A = anion, n = 1-2)
class LREH-II	$\text{Ln}(\text{OH})_2(\text{A}^{m-})_{1/m}\cdot n\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (n = 0-2)
class LREH-III	$\text{Ln}_2(\text{OH})_{5-x}(\text{A}^{m-})_{(1+x)/m}\cdot n\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (n = 0-2; $0 < x < 1$)
boehmite	AlOOH
antimony oxohydroxide	$[\text{Sb}_4\text{O}_4(\text{OH})_2](\text{O}_3\text{SCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{SO}_3)\cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$

The layered structure is characteristic not only of inorganic substances (Table 1), but also of many other materials. Laminated rods and slabs are essential elements of many modern structures. They play one of the leading roles in rocket, space and aviation technology, automobile and shipbuilding, chemical and power engineering, industrial and housing construction [40]. Deformable layered structures made of polymer composite materials are widely used in technology as elements of load-bearing structures [41].

Mathematical models of splitting layered structures. In [40, 42], a new method was developed for solving problems in the spatial theory of elasticity in the Saint-Venant formulation - the asymptotic splitting

method. The application of the asymptotic splitting method to problems of longitudinal-transverse bending of layered slabs with an arbitrary arrangement and number of layers is substantiated. It has been established that for surface loads that are m-harmonic functions, the method provides an exact analytical solution. The application of the asymptotic splitting method to the study of the edge effect in layered orthotropic composites is justified. Moreover, previously known analytical solutions for homogeneous single-layer structures, obtained either using Airy functions or the symbolic Lurie method, are also obtained using the asymptotic splitting method. In terms of historical con-

tinuity, the method of asymptotic splitting is a development of the ideas laid down by Navier, Poisson, Cauchy and Saint-Venant, and then by Mitchell and Almanzi.

In [41, 43], a method of regularization of the incorrect according to A.N. Tikhonov problem on the deformation of a volumetric incompressible medium, in which the limit of the solution of the regularized problem is explicitly calculated. A mathematical model of static deformation of axisymmetric layered structures containing elastic orthotropic and elastic volumetrically incompressible layers has been constructed using a developed regularization method. The sensitivity of the numerical solution to changes in the initial value of Poisson's ratio and the dimensions of the finite elements has been studied. It is shown that with the same number of iterations and with sequential refinement of the mesh, the solution converges faster to the analytical one when choosing the initial Poisson's ratio in the range of 0.3-0.35 than with values close to 0.5. The following characteristics of graphite are given in [44]: apparent density 1860-1960 kg/m³, tensile strength 14.7 MPa, compressive strength 67 MPa, elastic modulus 8.8 GPa, thermal conductivity 130 W/(m K) at 20 °C, LTLE 6.6 10⁻⁶ 1/K, electrical resistivity 5-8 μOhm m, emissivity at 2300 °C 0.85. Poisson's ratio $\mu = 14.7/67 = 0.22$.

In [38], for the first time, in a one-stage process with a bipolar supply of potential, various nanocomposites of few-layer graphene structures with transition metal oxides were simultaneously obtained in two electrochemical reactors isolated from each other. For pulsed action, a phenomenological model of one-stage plasma-electrochemical splitting of graphite with the formation of few-layer graphene structures was proposed for the first time. In [38, 40, 41], a detailed literature review of mathematical models of splitting layered structures was carried out, but we will limit ourselves only to work [45].

The scientific value of the work [45] lies in the construction of methods for mathematical modeling of the process of chemical pressing of oxidized graphite, the development and testing of methods for solving emerging boundary value problems with a moving interface between regions (Stefan type problems). Numerical experiments show the influence of the thermo-physical parameters of thermally expanded graphite on

the characteristics of the foaming process, such as the process time and the propagation of phase interfaces over time - a typical Stefan problem. Let us note the following: from a mathematical point of view, Stefan boundary value problems are fundamentally different from classical problems of heat conduction or diffusion. Due to the time dependence of the size of the flow transfer region, the classical methods of separation of variables and integral Fourier transforms are not applicable to this type of problem, since, while remaining within the framework of the methods of mathematical physics, it is not possible to coordinate the solution of the heat equation with the motion of the phase boundary. Stefan's problem has been treated both analytically and numerically since the end of the 19th century. A review of these works can be found in monographs [46-52], and especially in [53].

Our model of graphite splitting

Let us consider the surface layer of graphite, from where the splitting of layered materials begins. In general, there are two approaches: the Gibbs approach [54], in which the surface layer is conventionally considered as a geometric surface without thickness; the approach of Van der Wals, Guggenheim, Rusanov, in which the surface layer is considered as a layer of finite thickness [55]. According to modern concepts [56, 57], the surface phase γ_1 is understood as an ultrathin film (surface layer) that is in equilibrium with the crystalline base, the properties and structure of which are different from the bulk properties of γ_2 . However, the question of the theoretical "thickness" of this surface layer for various substances remained open until 2018. Only after our work [58-60] it became clear how the thickness of the surface layer, which plays a big role in nanotechnology, can be theoretically determined [61]. Thus, the surface layer, which we denote as R(I), its thickness is equal according to our model [58-60]:

$$R(I) = 0,17 \cdot 10^{-9} \nu = 0,17 \cdot 10^{-9} \cdot \dot{I} / \rho \text{ (m)}. \quad (1)$$

Equation (1) shows that the layer R(I) is determined by the parameter – the molar (atomic) volume of the metal ($\nu = M/\rho$, M – molar mass, ρ – density).

Its diagram is shown in Fig. 6a, and in Fig. 6b shows table D.I. Mendeleev with a periodic dependence of volume ν on Z.

Figure 6. Schematic representation of the surface layer (a), periodic change in the atomic volume of elements (b)

From Fig. 6b carbon is at the beginning of the periodic table next to boron. Using formula (1), we calculate $R(I)$ (Table 2) for graphite parallel to the plane (where the carbon hexagon lies) $x = a = b$ and perpendicular to this plane $x = c$.

Table 2.

Graphite parameters.

Graphite	ρ , g/sm ³	T_m , K	$R(I)_a$, nm	$R(I)_c$, nm	γ_a , mJ/m ²	γ_c , mJ/m ²
C	1,91	3970 K	1,07 (4)	2,92 (4)	2779	591

The anisotropy of graphite was determined using our formula [60]:

$$\begin{aligned} R(I) &= 0,17 \cdot 10^{-9} \cdot \dot{l} / \rho, \\ R(I)_{\delta=\dot{a}} &= 0,4 \cdot 10^{-11} \cdot \dot{\delta}(\dot{a})^3, \\ R(I)_{y=b} &= 0,4 \cdot 10^{-11} \cdot y(b)^3, \\ R(I)_{z=c} &= 0,4 \cdot 10^{-11} \cdot z(c)^3, \\ \gamma_{\dot{a}} &= 0,7 \cdot 10^{-3} \cdot \dot{O}_m \cdot R(I)_{\dot{a}} / R(I), \\ \gamma_b &= 0,7 \cdot 10^{-3} \cdot \dot{O}_m \cdot R(I)_b / R(I), \\ \gamma_c &= 0,7 \cdot 10^{-3} \cdot \dot{O}_m \cdot R(I)_{\dot{n}} / R(I). \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

In formula (2), γ is the surface energy of graphite faces, which is equal, according to the empirical formula [62]:

$$\gamma = 0,70 \cdot 10^{-3} \cdot T_m \quad [\text{J/m}^2], \quad (3)$$

In Table 2, the number in brackets $n = R(I)/a, c$ is equal to the number of graphene layers, and, c is the lattice constant along and across the graphite plane.

To split graphite over a layer of thickness $R(I)$, it is necessary to expend energy, which is called adhesion energy and is determined by the Dupre formula [63]:

$$W_{\dot{a}} = \gamma_1 + \gamma_2 - \gamma_{12} \approx \gamma_1 + \gamma_2, \quad (4)$$

where γ_1 , γ_2 and γ_{12} are the surface energy of the $R(I)$ layer, bulk phase and transition layer, which is negligible.

In [64], we showed that $\gamma_1 \approx 0.3 \gamma_2$, i.e. the surface energy of the $R(I)$ layer is three times less than the bulk phase. This means that the $R(I)$ layer will more easily move along the cleavage plane. At the boundary of the

$R(I)$ layer with the bulk phase, internal stresses arise due to relaxation or reconstruction of the surface [56]. These stresses lead to the formation of nanocracks with dimensions $R(I) = L_{nm}$ [64]. This fact was noticed 100 years ago. In the 20s of the twentieth century, academician A.F. Ioffe conducted a series of experiments with a NaCl crystal and he obtained a fracture of this salt in the amount of 0.4 g/mm² instead of 200 g/mm² according to Max Born's quatummechanical theory. A.F. Ioffe related this to the existence of microcracks in the surface layer. Then he dipped a NaCl crystal into water and measured the hardness of its surface, which increased as the surface dissolved, approaching the theoretical value [65]. This experiment was called the "Ioffe effect" [66]. Thus, for a NaCl crystal, according to our model, $R(I) = 4.6$ nm (which is typical for nanostructures) and the number of monolayers $n = R(I)/a = 8$ (a is the lattice constant). It is not difficult to wash off 8 monolayers of NaCl with water to obtain the Ioffe effect. In the same years, Griffiths examined the change in the energy of a body with a crack $L(G)$ under loading and obtained an energy criterion for destruction, according to which a crack acquires the ability to propagate only when the rate of release of elastic energy $\sigma \dot{\epsilon}$ during growth becomes equal to or exceeds the energy of the newly formed surface.

Internal voltages $\sigma \dot{\epsilon}$ between phases γ_1 and γ_2 can be calculated using the formula [19]:

$$\sigma_{is} = \sqrt{W_a \cdot \dot{A} / R(I)}, \quad (5)$$

where E is Young's modulus of elasticity.

Using equations (1) – (5), we calculate the elastic parameters for graphite.

Table 3.

Elastic parameters of graphite

Graphite	W_{aa} , J/m ²	W_{ac} , J/m ²	σ_{isa} , MPa	σ_{isc} , MPa	E_a , GPa	E_c , GPa
C ($\rho = 2,26$)	3,613	1,323	5740	1370	7,59	3,48

Next, we will build a theoretical model of graphite, representing it in the form of a cylinder of finite dimensions, and use our modified work [68, 69], supplementing it with homogeneous boundary conditions. In this case, we will calculate the stress gradient in the layer $R(I)$ using standard expressions [70].

The components of thermoelastic stress along the radius r - σ_r and along the z axis - σ_z - of the layer $R(I)$ will be assessed using the well-known equations [70]:

$$\sigma_r = -2G \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial T}{\partial r}. \quad (6)$$

$$\sigma_z = -2G \frac{\partial T}{\partial z}. \quad (7)$$

Here the shear modulus G is determined by the expression:

$$2G = \frac{E}{1 + \mu}, \quad (8)$$

where E is Young's modulus, μ is Poisson's ratio.

For graphite $E = 8.8$ GPa, $\mu = 0.22$, which means $2G = 7.21$ GPa.

From equations (6) and (7) we need to determine temperature gradients. To calculate the stress in the layer $R(I)$, when the process of graphite splitting is in progress, we come to a problem with a moving phase boundary, which is called the Stefan problem [45-53] (see above).

In this case, the nonstationary heat equation in a moving cylindrical coordinate system moving according to the law $\beta(t)$ has the form:

$$\frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = \ddot{A} \left[\frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial z^2} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r \frac{\partial T}{\partial r} \right) \right], \quad (9)$$

where D is the thermal diffusivity coefficient.

We choose the initial and boundary conditions in general form:

$$T(r, z, t)|_{t=0} = \varphi(r, z),$$

$$T(r, z, t)|_{r=R} = \gamma(z, t),$$

$$T(r, z, t)|_{z=0} = \gamma_1(r, t),$$

$$T(r, z, t)|_{z=\beta(t)} = \gamma_2(r, t).$$

The functions $\beta(t)$, $\varphi(z, t)$, $\gamma(z, t)$, $\gamma_1(r, t)$, $\gamma_2(r, t)$ will be considered continuous. We look for a solution to the problem in the form:

$$T(r, z, t) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} J_0(\lambda_{0k} r) \left\{ e^{-\lambda_{0k}^2 t} \left[\frac{1}{2\sqrt{\pi}} \int_0^t e^{-\frac{(z-\xi)^2}{4\lambda_{0k}^2 t}} d\xi \right. \right. \\ \times \left(\int_0^{\ell} \varphi(r, \xi) I_0(\lambda_{0k} r) r dr \right) d\xi + \frac{R I_1(\lambda_{0k} R)}{2\sqrt{\pi}} \int_0^t d\tau \int_0^{\ell} \frac{\gamma(\xi, \tau)}{\sqrt{t-\tau}} e^{-\lambda_{0k}^2 (t-\tau)} d\xi + \\ \left. \left. + \frac{1}{4\sqrt{\pi}} \int_0^t \frac{z}{[\ddot{A}(t-\tau)]^{3/2}} e^{-\frac{z^2}{4\ddot{A}(t-\tau)}} K_1(\tau) d\tau + \frac{1}{4\sqrt{\pi}} \int_0^t \frac{z-\beta(\tau)}{[\ddot{A}(t-\tau)]^{3/2}} e^{-\frac{[z-\beta(\tau)]^2}{4\ddot{A}(t-\tau)}} K_2(\tau) d\tau \right] \right\}. \quad (13)$$

To use equations (6)-(8), we simplify the general problem (13) by taking homogeneous boundary conditions. In this case:

$$\frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = \ddot{A} \left[\frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial z^2} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r \frac{\partial T}{\partial r} \right) \right] \quad (14)$$

$$\left. \begin{aligned} T(r, z, t)|_{t=0} &= 0; \\ T(r, z, t)|_{r=R} &= T_0 = \text{const}; \\ T(r, z, t)|_{z=0} &= T_0 = \text{const}; \\ T(r, z, t)|_{z=\beta(t)} &= T_0 = \text{const} \end{aligned} \right\}, \quad (15)$$

where T_0 is the temperature value on the surface of the cylinder and on the moving interface. Then the general solution to the problem will take the form:

$$T(r, z, t) = \sum_{\tilde{k}=0}^{\infty} I_0(\lambda_{0\tilde{k}} r) \left\{ e^{-\lambda_{0\tilde{k}}^2 t} \left[\frac{R I_1(\lambda_{0\tilde{k}} R)}{2\sqrt{\pi} \ddot{A}} \int_0^t d\tau \int_0^H \frac{\tilde{N}_1}{\sqrt{t-\tau}} \times \right. \right. \\ \times e^{-\lambda_{0\tilde{k}}^2 (t-\tau)} d\xi + \frac{1}{4\sqrt{\pi}} \int_0^t \frac{z}{[\ddot{A}(t-\tau)]^{3/2}} e^{-\frac{z^2}{4\ddot{A}(t-\tau)}} K_1(\tau) d\tau + \\ \left. \left. + \frac{1}{4\sqrt{\pi}} \int_0^t \frac{z-\beta(\tau)}{[\ddot{A}(t-\tau)]^{3/2}} e^{-\frac{[z-\beta(\tau)]^2}{4\ddot{A}(t-\tau)}} K_2(\tau) d\tau \right] \right\}. \quad (16)$$

Limiting ourselves to the first term in sum (16), for stationary temperature we have the following expression:

$$T(r, z, t) = \ddot{O}_0 J_0 \left(\frac{2r}{R} \right) e^{-\lambda_{0\tilde{k}}^2 t} \left\{ \frac{e^2 J_0 \left(\frac{2r}{R} \right)}{16 \ddot{A}^{3/2}} \ln t + \frac{L J_1 \left(\frac{2r}{R} \right)}{16 \ddot{A}^{3/2}} e^{-\lambda_{0\tilde{k}}^2 t} \ln(t-1) + \right.$$

$$T(r, z, t) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \bar{T}_k(z, t) I_0(\lambda_{0k} r), \quad (10)$$

where λ_{0k} are the roots of the equation

$$I_0(\lambda_{0k} R) = 0$$

and $I_0(\lambda_{0k} R)$ is the zeroth order Bessel function satisfying the equation:

$$\frac{1}{r} \frac{d}{dr} \left[r \frac{dI(\lambda_{0k} r)}{dr} \right] + I_0(\lambda_{0k} r) = 0, \quad (11)$$

$$\bar{T}_k(z, t) = \int_0^R T_k(r, z, t) I_0(\lambda_{0k} r) r dr. \quad (12)$$

The final solution to this problem looks like this:

$$+ \left(1 - \frac{1}{\sqrt{t}}\right) \left(\frac{D}{z\pi} + \frac{D^{3/2}}{\pi^2 z\beta(t)} \right) + \left(1 - \frac{1}{\sqrt{t}}\right) \frac{2\sqrt{\delta}}{\sqrt{\pi}} \frac{1}{[z - \beta(t)]} \Bigg\}, \quad (17)$$

When deriving (17), we took into account that the equation $I_0(\lambda_{or})=0$ implies $\lambda_0=2r/R$ and $I_1(2)=1$. In equation (17): $D = \lambda/C_p \rho$ - thermal diffusivity coefficient, λ - thermal conductivity, C_p - specific heat capacity, ρ - density. For graphite at $T = 300$ K: $\lambda = 195$ W/m K; $C_p = 710$ J/kg K; $\rho = 1910$ kg/m³; $D = 1.44 \cdot 10^{-4}$ m²/s;

If the time t is very large, then as a result we get:

$$\dot{O}(r, z, t) = \frac{\ddot{A}^{3/2} \cdot \dot{O}_0}{\pi^2} J_0\left(\frac{2r}{R}\right) \cdot \frac{t}{z\beta(t)}, \quad (18)$$

Let us use the asymptotic representation of the Bessel functions [71], then we obtain:

$$T(r, z, t) = \frac{D^{3/2} \cdot \dot{O}_0}{\pi^{5/2}} \sqrt{\frac{R}{r}} \cdot \frac{t}{z \cdot \beta(t)}, \quad (19)$$

The radial and axial components of the temperature gradient will be equal:

$$\frac{\partial T}{\partial r} = \frac{2\ddot{A}^{3/2} \cdot \dot{O}_0 \cdot \sqrt{r \cdot R}}{\pi^2} \cdot \frac{t}{z\beta(t)}, \quad (20)$$

$$\frac{\partial \dot{O}}{\partial z} = \frac{\ddot{A}^{3/2} \cdot \dot{O}_0}{\pi^2} J_0\left(\frac{2r}{R}\right) \cdot \frac{2t}{z^2\beta(t)}. \quad (21)$$

We will analyze only the radial component from equation (6), since it leads to a shift of graphite layers and its splitting:

$$\sigma_r = \frac{4\ddot{A}^{3/2} \cdot \dot{O}_0 \cdot G \cdot \sqrt{r \cdot R}}{\pi^2 \cdot r} \cdot \frac{t}{z\beta(t)}. \quad (22)$$

Let us take $r = R$, $z = \beta(t)$, then we get:

$$\beta(t) = \frac{2\ddot{A}^{3/4}}{\pi} \cdot \sqrt{\dot{O}_0} \cdot \sqrt{\frac{G}{\sigma_r}} \cdot \sqrt{t} = \beta_0 \cdot \sqrt{t}. \quad (23)$$

Equation (23) mathematically coincides with Stefan's fourth problem, where the freezing of ice is considered, and the movement of phase boundaries $\beta(t) = \beta_0\sqrt{t}$ is called the self-similar law of motion. This issue is discussed in detail in the work of Lyubov B.M. [47].

Solutions (18) will look as shown in Fig. 7a.

Figure 7. Graphs of Bessel functions (a) and deformation of highly compressed metals (b).

In Fig. 7b shows [72] that a comparison of longitudinal and transverse deformations of highly compressed metals also showed their periodic nature. The experimental and theoretical results we obtained fit into the model of macroscopic localization of plastic flow developed in [73]. This work shows that the localization of plastic flow in solids has a pronounced wave character. Moreover, at the stages of easy sliding, linear and parabolic strain hardening, as well as at the stage of preliminary destruction, the observed localization patterns are different types of wave processes. Analysis of the wave characteristics of such processes made it possible to measure the speed of their propagation ($\sim 10^{-4}$ m/s), wavelength ($\sim 10^{-2}$ m) and establish that the dispersion relation for such waves is quadratic.

Now let's turn to equation (23), where $\beta(t) = \beta_0 \sqrt{t}$, $\beta_0 = 0.23 \sqrt{t}$.

The components of thermoelastic stresses along the radius r - σ_r will have the form:

$$\sigma_r = \frac{4\ddot{A}^{3/2} \cdot \dot{O}_0 \cdot G \cdot \sqrt{r \cdot R}}{\pi^2 \cdot r} \cdot \frac{t}{z\beta(t)}. \quad (24)$$

Let us take $r = R$, $z = \beta(t)$, then we get:

$$\sigma_r = \frac{4\ddot{A}^{3/2} \cdot \dot{O}_0 \cdot G \cdot t}{\pi^2 \cdot \beta(t)^2} = \frac{80\ddot{A}^{3/2} \cdot G}{\pi^2} \approx 8\ddot{A}^{3/2} \cdot G. \quad (25)$$

Components of thermoelastic stresses for graphite $\sigma_r = 0.24$ MPa, which are formed at the interphase boundary separating the R(I) layer from the rest of the volume and associated with relaxation or reconstruction of the graphite surface during its formation. If we compare σ_r with elastic stresses σ_{isc} from table. 3, then their difference is visible by almost three orders of magnitude. This means that it is much easier to obtain graphene mechanically (including ultrasonic splitting, see above) than by changing the temperature gradient.

The components of thermoelastic stresses at the interface are quite difficult to determine. In [74], thermoelastic stresses were calculated in a profiled sapphire single crystal, having the shape of a round rod with a diameter of 10 mm, a length of 100 mm (small parameter $\varepsilon = 0.05$) and grown from a melt using the Stepanov method. Since the given formulas are approximate, the maximum value of this component is $\sigma_r = 1.42$ MPa, which is higher than that of graphite. This is due to the fact that graphite's Young's modulus is two orders of magnitude lower than that of sapphire.

According to the principles of thermoelasticity [75], thermoelastic stresses at the interface can be determined by the formula: $\sigma_r = \alpha E_c \Delta T$, $\alpha = \text{const}$. The constant α has not been defined anywhere, so we will determine it using the data from table. 3 and the above value of σ_r . As a result we get:

$$\sigma_r = 10^{-2} \beta^2 \cdot \dot{A}_n \cdot \Delta \dot{O}, \quad (26)$$

where β is the linear expansion coefficient.

Equation (26) shows that it is possible to split graphite using a pulsed picosecond laser ($\beta_2 \sim 10^{-12}$) of the Nd-YAG type for heating. In [76], researchers from the Univ. of Nebraska (USA), together with Chinese scientists, have developed a new approach to producing graphene, based on the exfoliation of crystalline graphite when exposed to laser radiation. A crystal of highly ordered pyrolytic graphite (HOPG) was used as a target, which was placed on a silicon substrate. Graphene synthesis was carried out in an argon atmosphere at a pressure of about 1 Torr. A commercial pulsed Nd:YAG laser with a wavelength of 532 nm, a pulse duration of 7 ns, and a pulse repetition rate of 1 Hz was used as the irradiation source. Laser irradiation provided an energy density on the target in the range from 0.8 to 20 J/cm². Carbon particles formed as a result of laser ablation of the graphite surface fell on the Si substrate. When the laser radiation energy density on the target was from 1 to 10 J/cm², thin flakes appeared on the HOPG surface, which spontaneously separated from the surface and fell on the surface of the substrate. The resulting graphene samples on a silicon substrate were examined using a scanning electron microscope (SEM), a high-resolution transmission electron microscope (HRTEM), an atomic force microscope (AFM), and a micron-resolution Raman spectrometer (laser wavelength 514 nm). Analysis of Raman spectra indicates that graphene samples consist of several (up to 10) layers. Measurements performed using AFM showed that the thickness of the graphene film is 3.9 nm. TEM images of a graphene film several microns in size indicate its wavy structure (see Fig. 7) and the presence of numerous bends.

In order to study the mechanism of formation of graphene sheets under the action of laser radiation, graphite tablets were used as a target along with HOPG samples. It turned out that irradiation of such tablets at an energy density of 0.8 to 20 J/cm² does not lead to the formation of graphene films, but is accompanied by the appearance of nanometer-sized amorphous carbon particles.

In [77], the structural properties and composition of carbon films obtained using pulsed laser evaporation of sublimated carbon tapes were studied. Studies have shown that the resulting films have a graphite-like structure with a low sp³ phase content and can be classified as nanocrystalline defective turbostratic graphite or graphene.

In [78], a study of the process of formation of extended graphitized microstructures in the volume of diamond under the influence of ultrashort and short laser pulses was carried out, as well as a study of the properties, internal structure and prospects for the practical application of these microstructures. Unique features of

local laser-induced graphitization, occurring at a considerable distance from the surface of the diamond crystal, have been revealed, which sharply limits the possibility of relaxation of the resulting mechanical stresses (see Table 3) and determines the emergence of a conductive nanostructured heterophase composite, which has also never been observed before. The research carried out laid the scientific foundations for the rapid development of promising technology for laser microstructuring of the volume of diamond crystals.

Conclusion

To split graphite over a layer of thickness R(I), it is necessary to expend energy, which is called adhesion energy and is determined by the Dupre formula. We have shown that $\gamma_1 \approx 0.3 \gamma_2$, i.e. the surface energy of the R(I) layer is three times less than the bulk phase. This means that the R(I) layer will more easily move along the cleavage plane. Using equations (1) – (5), we calculated the elastic parameters for graphite. To calculate the stress in the layer R(I), when the process of graphite splitting occurs, we come to a problem with a moving phase boundary, which is called the Stefan problem. Our experimental and theoretical results fit into the model of macroscopic localization of plastic flow. The localization of plastic flow in solids has a pronounced wave character. Moreover, at the stages of easy sliding, linear and parabolic strain hardening, as well as at the stage of preliminary destruction, the observed localization patterns are different types of wave processes. Analysis of the wave characteristics of such processes made it possible to measure the speed of their propagation ($\sim 10^{-4}$ m/s), wavelength ($\sim 10^{-2}$ m) and establish that the dispersion relation for such waves is quadratic. According to our proposed model, the components of thermoelastic stresses for graphite are $\sigma = 0.24$ MPa, which are formed at the interphase boundary separating the R(I) layer from the rest of the volume and are associated with relaxation or reconstruction of the graphite surface during its formation. If we compare σ with elastic stresses σ_{isc} from table. 3, then their difference is visible by almost three orders of magnitude. This means that it is much easier to obtain graphene mechanically (including ultrasonic splitting) than by changing the temperature gradient.

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